

9. A. S. BULL, R. B. MARTIN and R. J. P. WILLIAMS in "Electronic Aspects of Biochemistry", ed. B. PULLMAN, Academic, New York, 1964, p. 524.
10. A. M. TAIT and D. H. BUSCH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, 15, 197.

Complexes of Oxomolybdenum(v) and Oxovanadium(IV) with Thiocarbohydrazones

A. KUMAR and L. K. MISHRA*

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-800 005

Manuscript received 10 May 1988, accepted 13 February 1989

THE complexes of some metal ions with thiocarbohydrazide and its various thiocarbohydrazone derivatives have been reported from this laboratory¹ and by others². In the present paper, we report the preparation and characterisation of some oxomolybdenum(v) and oxovanadium(IV) complexes of thiocarbohydrazide (tch) and mono-thiocarbohydrazones derived from acetone (actcH), acetophenone (aptcH), benzaldehyde (bztcH) and furfural (futcH).

Experimental

The ligands and $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$ were prepared by the reported methods³.

Preparation of complexes. $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5\text{L}_n].n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{LH}=\text{tch}, \text{actcH}, \text{aptcH}, \text{bztcH}, \text{futcH}$; $n=1$ to 4) : $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$ (0.005 mol) dissolved in methanol (30–40 ml) was treated with 1 : 2 molar ratio of thiocarbohydrazide or thiocarbohydrazones dissolved

either in methanol or methanol–dimethylformamide mixture (30–40 ml). The solution was refluxed for 0.5 h on a steam-bath when products separated out either gradually or on dilution with equal volume of water. The solid complexes were filtered, washed with aqueous methanol and dried (CaCl_2). The purity of the complexes was ascertained by paper chromatography.

$[\text{VO}(\text{tch})\text{SO}_4]$ and $[\text{VOL}_n].n\text{H}_2\text{O}$: An aqueous methanolic solution of $\text{VOSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.01 mol in 50–60 ml) was treated in 1 : 1 molar ratio with the solutions of aforesaid ligands dissolved in methanol or methanol–dimethylformamide mixture (50–60 ml). The contents were refluxed for 30–40 min on a steam-bath when products separated out either on cooling or on raising pH of the solutions by adding aqueous sodium acetate solution (4–5 ml). The solid complexes were dried as above. The purity of the complexes was checked by paper chromatography.

Magnetic susceptibilities were measured on a Gouy balance at room temperature ($30 \pm 2^\circ$). Electronic absorption spectra (dioxane) were recorded at C.D.R.I., Lucknow and infrared spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer. The analytical and physical data of the compounds are listed in Table I.

Results and Discussion

The complex $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$ undergoes substitution reaction with thiocarbohydrazide and thiocarbohydrazones forming μ -oxodioxomolybdenum(v) complexes $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5\text{L}_n].n\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Vanadyl sulphate gave $[\text{VO}(\text{tch})\text{SO}_4]$ and $[\text{VOL}_n].n\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The complexes have poor solubility in benzene and chloroform but dissolve appreciably in dimethyl-

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} B.M.
			Metal	N	O	H	
$[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5(\text{tch})_4].4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Black	250	26.59 (26.19)	30.12 (30.59)	6.17 (6.55)	3.54 (3.85)	Dia.
$[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5(\text{actc})_4].3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Black	250	21.51 (21.93)	25.30 (25.61)	21.52 (21.96)	4.52 (4.83)	Dia.
$[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5(\text{aptc})_4].4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Black	160	16.52 (16.81)	19.31 (19.64)	37.44 (37.89)	4.23 (4.59)	Dia.
$[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5(\text{bztc})_4].4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Green	175	17.90 (17.68)	20.33 (20.65)	35.80 (35.42)	4.52 (4.08)	Dia.
$[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_5(\text{futc})_4].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Blood red	250	19.40 (19.02)	22.60 (22.21)	28.12 (28.56)	3.88 (3.19)	Dia.
$[\text{VO}(\text{tch})\text{SO}_4]^b$	Black	250	18.51 (18.92)	20.54 (20.81)	4.15 (4.46)	2.50 (2.24)	1.62
$[\text{VO}(\text{actc})_2].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Coffee	250	12.45 (12.94)	28.10 (28.48)	24.22 (24.42)	5.30 (5.63)	1.79
$[\text{VO}(\text{aptc})_2].3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Gray	250	9.12 (9.51)	20.53 (20.92)	40.75 (40.36)	5.51 (5.26)	1.79
$[\text{VO}(\text{bztc})_2].\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Green	210	10.52 (10.80)	23.34 (23.76)	40.50 (40.76)	4.55 (4.27)	1.63
$[\text{VO}(\text{futc})_2].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Green	250	10.45 (10.85)	23.52 (23.87)	30.45 (30.70)	3.55 (3.86)	1.72

*tch = thiocarbohydrazide, actcH = acetone thiocarbohydrazone, aptcH = acetophenone thiocarbohydrazone, bztcH = benzaldehyde thiocarbohydrazone and futcH = furfural thiocarbohydrazone. ^bAnalysis sulphate, Found : 35.95. Requires : 35.68%.

formamide and dioxane. The hydrated complexes lose associated water molecules below 120°. The loss of water molecules at low temperature indicates that they are uncoordinated. The failure of these compounds to form pyridine or picoline adducts further support the uncoordinated nature of water molecules.

The oxomolybdenum(v) complexes are diamagnetic (Table 1) similar to dinuclear μ -oxomolybdenum(v) complexes⁴. Vanadyl complexes show normal magnetic moment values indicating absence of exchange interaction in the complexes. Oxomolybdenum(v) complexes are dark brown or brickred in colour and do not display well resolved absorption bands in the visible region. In some complexes two or three broad and weak absorption bands are observed in the regions 22 500–24 500, 19 500–21 800 and 13 800–15 200 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^3B_2 \rightarrow {}^3E(II)$, ${}^3B_2 \rightarrow {}^3B_1$ and ${}^3B_2 \rightarrow {}^3E(I)$ transitions respectively in distorted octahedral field⁵. Oxovanadium(IV) complex $[\text{VO}(\text{tcH})\text{SO}_4]$ displays a shoulder at 17 280 and a medium band at 19 600 cm^{-1} assignable to $b_2 \rightarrow a_1^*$ and $b_2 \rightarrow e_g^*$ transitions⁶. The complexes $[\text{VO}L_2] \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ display ligand field transitions at 21 000 and 17 580 cm^{-1} as broad and weak bands.

The infrared spectra of tcH displays NH stretch at 3 280 and 3 200 cm^{-1} which shifted to lower frequency by 30–50 cm^{-1} on complexation indicating coordination of NH_2 nitrogen. The NH stretches of thiocarbohydrazones located near 3 150–3 320 cm^{-1} are observed as broad band due to mixing of OH stretch of water molecules and NH stretches of NH and NH_2 groups in the complexes. The $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ of ligands are obtained at 850–880 cm^{-1} which shifted to lower frequency in the complexes by 50–80 cm^{-1} indicating the coordination of thioamide sulphur with metal atom. The δ_{NH_2} of thiocarbohydrazone observed at $1\,610 \pm 10$ cm^{-1} is not affected appreciable in the complexes indicating that the terminal NH_2 nitrogen is not involved in coordination.

The nature and position of Mo=O stretch has been taken as diagnostic of monomeric and dimeric μ -oxo complexes of oxomolybdenum(v). The oxomolybdenum(v) complexes display a broad and very strong band at 950–970 cm^{-1} . The

$\nu(\text{Mo} \begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \diagdown \\ \text{---} \end{array} \text{Mo})$ band has been found at 810–850 cm^{-1} supporting the oxo-bridging in the complexes. In the vanadyl complexes $\nu_{\text{V=O}}$ is seen at 970–930 cm^{-1} (the normal range of V=O group) indicates that V=O oxygen is not involved in dimerisation or polymerisation⁷.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (A.K.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi for the award of a Teacher Fellowship.

References

1. R. SINGH, J. P. SHRIVASTAVA and L. K. MISHRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, **15**, 805.
2. F. KURZER and M. WILKINSON, *Chem. Rev.*, 1970, **70**, 145, G. R. BURNS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 277, A. BRAIBANTI, F. DALLAVALLE, E. LEFORATI and M. A. PALLINGHALLI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1968, **2**, 449, F. BIGOLI, A. BRAIBANTI, A. M. M. LANFREDI, A. TIRIPICCHIO and M. T. GAMBELLINI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1971, **5**, 449.
3. T. A. GEORG and C. D. SELBOLD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 6859, L. F. AUDRIETH, E. S. SCOTT and P. S. KIPPUR, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1954, **19**, 733, J. SANDSTROM, *Acta Chem. Scand*, 1960, **14**, 1037, 1939.
4. F. A. COTTON and N. F. CURTIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 241.
5. A. SABATINI and J. BERTINI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 204; R. N. JOWITT and P. C. H. MITCHELL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 1702, C. R. HARE and H. B. GRAY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 363.
6. S. M. HORNER, S. Y. TYRRE and D. L. VENEZKY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 844, C. J. BALLHAUSSEN and H. B. GRAY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 111.
7. J. SELBIN, H. R. MANNING and G. OESSAC, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1963, **25**, 253.

Complexes of Copper(II), Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) with *N*-Acetyl-*N'*-phenylthiocarbamide

R. K. PATEL* and R. N. PATEL

Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College, Rourkela-769 008

Manuscript received 11 April 1988, revised 25 November 1988, accepted 13 February 1989

TRANSITION metal complexes of sulphur donor ligand are finding extensive uses¹. The present paper reports the preparation and study the complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with *N*-acetyl-*N'*-phenylthiocarbamide (APTC).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. *N*-Acetyl-*N'*-phenylthiocarbamide was prepared following the reported procedure². An alcoholic solution of the metal salt was added to a solution of the ligand in acetone with 1 : 1 molar ratio. The resulting mixture was stirred vigorously when a coloured compound precipitated which was filtered, washed with alcohol followed by acetone and dried under reduced pressure. Attempts to prepare the perchlorate complexes of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} and the bromo complex of Ni^{II} were unsuccessful. The complexes were found to be highly insoluble in water but sparingly soluble in common organic solvents.

The analytical³ and physical data of the complexes are given in Table 1. The magnetic susceptibility were measured at room temperature